

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: Amir****FIRST NAME: Sharon****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE : ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Pr. Laurent Cleenewerck**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.
The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)
The author used MSWord 2016 on Windows 10

KEY CONCEPTS OF ESSAY WRITING

This response paper will outline the key concepts from the ACA-401 assigned reading material including the *ACA-401 Coursepack for period one (1)* and *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*.

1) INTRODUCTION

The mandatory Euclid course called *International Academic Writing - ACA-401D*, provides an overall review of the main principles of academic writing and outlines the basic techniques and styles used for writing academic research papers.

The *ACA-401 Coursepack for period one (1)* presents valuable information regarding academic essay writing, outlining the typical structure of an academic essay which includes an introduction, body and conclusion. It also reviews the importance of using correct citations to avoid plagiarism and outlines various style guides that are used for essay writing. In this response paper I will summarize those main principles.

2) ESSAY STRUCTURE

A typical academic essay introduces readers to a main idea, concept or theory (i.e., main thesis), which is supported on evidence and examples, backed up by various accredited sources (EUCLID 2015, 2). The essay is structured with main paragraphs, starting with the general introduction to the topic and moves on to the main body of the essay where the author backs up the findings and ideas with evidence from various sources, and follows to the conclusion of the essay where the main findings of the thesis are summarized (EUCLID 2015, 5).

3) CITATIONS

Citation styles are a set of guidelines or rules for referencing sources of material in academic writing. It is important to give credit to the original source of ideas and facts that are used in any academic writing. By using correct citations, writers avoid plagiarism.

There are two main citation styles that are noted in the Turabian guide: notes citation style, and author-date citation style (Turabian 2018, 139-148).

a) Notes Style

In notes style citation, a subscript number is placed at the end of the quote or the end of the sentence to indicate any material that is supplementing the text itself, including the bibliographic reference source. The Turabian style uses both endnotes and footnotes.

i) *Footnotes*

Footnotes appear at the bottom of the page where the superscript number appears. Footnotes can cite a source reference or an explanation/comment (which is not directly related to the argument of the paragraph).

ii) *Endnotes*

Endnotes will appear at the end of the written work, either at the end of the chapter (for example in a book) or at the end of the written document. It may appear on a separate page of an essay.

b) Author-Date Style

In the author-date citation, the source is used in the actual text, by placing following information at the end of the sentence: (author, date and page number). The full reference list will outline the correct bibliography of all sources at the end of the document.

4) STYLE GUIDES

Most writers follow a consistent style of writing throughout their work, to ensure uniformity of writing. Style guides include the correct use of grammar and punctuation in addition to the overall formatting, layout and correct citations of documents (EUCLID 2015, 52).

It is recommended to use *The Chicago Manual of Style*, which is also known as the ‘Turabian style’ for all major papers and reports produced at Euclid University. Part III of the book *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations* outlines the guidelines of the ‘Turabian style’ including the following:

- I. Spelling
- II. Punctuation
- III. Names, Special Terms, and Titles of Works
- IV. Numbers
- V. Abbreviations
- VI. Quotations
- VII. Tables and Figures

By following the guidelines outlined in the Manual, students and researches can produce reports that are consistent in style.

5) CONCLUSION

The assigned reading material for the first lesson of course ACA-401 will be used as my reference guide for future writing response papers and academic research for Euclid University. Together with the Turabian Manual, the above-mentioned sources summarize the basic principles and guidelines for drafting and editing academic writings, using the Chicago rule of style.

I found the assigned reading material to be very useful and informative. The content of the Turabian Manual is especially valuable for my current work as I use the Chicago Manual Style (along with the UN Editorial Manual) for editing documents at the United Nations Economic and Social Commission for Asia and the Pacific.

REFERENCES

EUCLID. 2015. ACA-401 Coursepack. Washington DC: Euclid University Press.
<https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1/> (accessed July 05, 2019)

Turabian, Kate L. 2018. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 9th edition. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.